

Failure mechanisms related to the fibre, the interface and the matrix properties during the fragmentation test.

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ABSTRACT

The fragmentation test is one of the most frequently used test to quantify the interface shear strength properties. Until now, a simple analytical model is used to derive from the experimental data average interfacial shear strength values. The limitations of this common approach are outlined in this paper by the presentation of fragmentation test results obtained with glass fibres embedded in polypropylene and in different epoxies. Depending on the interface, the interphase or the matrix properties different kinds of cracks, initiated at the fibre ruptures, can propagate. A careful analysis of all the phenomena which occur during the test is performed so that the validity of the derived interfacial shear strength values can be confirmed.

Keywords : interface, fragmentation, decohesion, matrix cracks

1. Introduction

The daily use of composites in an increasing number of applications has led the scientific community to know better the characteristics of each components of a composite in order to improve the existing products. Therefore, micromechanical test techniques were developed to have more insight in the micromechanical properties of the interface region which ensures the link between the fibre and the matrix. One of these micromechanical test techniques is the fragmentation test, during which a matrix coupon containing a single fibre is loaded in tension. This technique is extensively used and has the great advantage that every critical phenomenon which takes place during the test (fibre fracture, decohesion between the fibre and the matrix, matrix cracks) can easily be visualised with the aid of an optical microscope using polarised light when the matrix is transparent. Nevertheless, it is surprising to note that, even if in few cases the occurrence of the typical phenomena are reported (1) (2), in most of the cases the simple formula of Kelly is used for the deduction of the interface shear strength out of the fibre length obtained at the saturation level (3). The test results presented in this paper will show that a well documented and analysed fragmentation test is rich in information about the properties of the interface in relation to the properties of the matrix and that the straightforward application of the simple Kelly formula can lead to erroneous results.

2. Materials

Fragmentation tests were performed on specimens containing two kinds of glass fibres (unsized, and sized) embedded in polypropylene or in two different epoxy matrices.

The unsized glass fibres come directly from a roving: it means that the fibres were wound onto a bobbin directly from the spinneret and no sizing was applied to the fibre. The sized fibres are fibres made to be pultruded with a thermoplastics, especially polyamide. This fibre can also be used with other thermoplastics for example polypropylene. The sizing is made out of a silane coupling agent and also an organic sticky system.

As the tensile strength of the fibre is an important factor which will influence the fragmentation process, the two fibres were tested in tension. The dependence of the fibre strength as a function of the fibre length for the two fibres is presented in figure 1. From these first results it appears that the sized fibres are stronger than the unsized fibres for the range of fibre lengths tested.

Concerning the matrices, the polypropylene utilised in this study is a homopolymer, supplied by DSM (Holland). This grade has outstanding flow properties combined with a relatively high stiffness and impact resistance. It is characterized by its high gloss and transparency.

One of the epoxy resin used was the Araldite LY 556 supplied by Ciba Geigy. This is an epoxy resin of the DGEBA family and the hardener used for this resin was diaminophenylmethane.

The last resin is a mixture of two epoxy resins: the Epikote 828 and the Epikote 871. The Epikote 871 is an aliphatic epoxy ester and when it is used with Epikote 828, it provides a flexible matrix. The curing agent used in this case is a diethyltoluenediamine.

In figure 2, the mechanical behaviour of the three resins is presented schematically

Fig.1 Fibre tensile strength properties

Fig. 2 Mechanical properties of the resins

3. Experimental techniques

The fragmentation tests were performed on specimens prepared by using silicone molds in the case of the epoxy resins and by cutting specimens out of a plate prepared with the hot press in the case of the polypropylene. During each test a region of the specimen (30 mm long) was continuously scanned and the number of fractures appearing in this region was noted as a function of the applied strain. The number of fractures was used to calculate an average fibre fragment length (L_f) and a aspect ratio ($S=L_f/D$). If decohesion took place along the fibre-matrix interface,

the decohesion length was also followed as a function of the applied strain and this value was related to the fibre fragment length along which the decohesion took place.

4. Results

As the phenomena occurring during the test were particular related to the matrix, the results obtained with the three resins will be first presented separately.

In the case of a polypropylene matrix, very few fibre ruptures appeared in the studied region (30 mm) and a saturation level was quickly reached. Moreover when a rupture of the fibre occurred, simultaneously debonding at the interface was observed. This decohesion developed continuously as a function of the applied strain (see figure 3). In figures 4 en 5 the evolution of the aspect ratio and of the decohesion length are presented as a function of the applied strain.

It is interesting to note that the first fibre fracture occurs more rapidly in the case of the unsized fibres than in the case of the sized fibres. Moreover the aspect ratio at saturation of the unsized fibre is lower than that of the sized fibre.

Fig. 3. Example of fibre fracture and decohesion in the case of the polypropylene matrix.

Fig. 4. Evolution of the aspect ratio for the unsized and the sized fibres embedded in polypropylene matrix.

Fig. 5. Evolution of the decohesion length for the unsized and the sized fibres embedded in a polypropylene matrix.

The same kind of comments concerning the type of phenomena which take place during the fragmentation process (decohesion) and the comparison between the two fibres are for the resin LY 556 (fig. 6). Nevertheless, in this case the absolute value of the first fibre fracture, the saturation level and the development of the decohesion were different (see table 1).

Fig. 6. Example of fibre fracture and decohesion in the case of the LY556 resin.

Completely different rupture mechanisms were followed with the resin Epikote 828/871. In this case a fibre fracture does not induce a decohesion process between the fibre and the matrix. The matrix fails and two cracks propagate into the matrix from the fibre fracture. On figure 7, a general view of three fibre ruptures and the consequent matrix cracks are shown for a strain of 8.2%. In general a fibre fracture induces the occurrence of two cracks in the matrix (lozenges shape). Sometimes a third matrix crack also appears between the two first cracks. While the fragmentation test continues, one of the two first matrix cracks becomes outstandingly bigger than the other one and when it reaches critical dimensions the specimen fractures due to the catastrophic propagation of this crack.

In this case also, independently of the fact that the failure mechanisms around the fibre fractures are completely different from those in the two first cases, the fibre still undergoes a fragmentation process as a function of the applied strain. A saturation level is also reached but in this case this occurs at a larger strain.

Fig. 7 Typical fibre ruptures and matrix cracks during the fragmentation of a fibre embedded in the resin 828/871.

In table 1, the fragmentation test results are summarized.

Materials	Studied region (mm)	Strain at first fibre fracture (%)	Number of fractures at saturation
Polypropylene	30	2.8	9
Unsized glass fibre Sized glass fibre		3.9	5
Epoxy LY556	15	3.0	63
Unsized glass fibre Sized glass fibre		3.7	32
Epikote 828/871	15	2.3	48
Unsized glass fibre Sized glass fibre		3.5	27

Table 1, fragmentation test results

5. Discussion

The fragmentation test has shown interesting differences in failure mechanisms around fragmented fibre ends. Some phenomena may be observed with all the matrices used and some others are particular to certain systems. As the tests have been performed to characterize the different interfaces and to analyse the possibilities of the fragmentation test, different points with regards to the experimental results are now discussed in more detail.

The first fibre fracture

With all the matrices used, the first fibre fracture did always occur more rapidly in the case of the unsized fibres than in the case of the sized fibres. This can be explained by the results of the fibre tensile tests. Indeed, the unsized fibres have a lower failure strain than the sized fibres and so, the unsized fibres will fracture first.

Nevertheless, the strain at which the first fibre fracture occurs, is not equal to the failure strain of the fibre. This is due to the fact that the fibre is embedded in the matrix and that the residual thermal stresses will bring the fibre in compression during the curing or the melting. Therefore, the strain at which the fibre fracture occurs gives a good indication of the value of the residual stresses present in the fibre after the preparation procedure.

Some authors (4) have used the information concerning the first fibre fracture to define an "interfacial transmissibility factor". This approach seems to be doubtful as the first fibre fracture is mostly influenced by the Weibull parameters of the tested fibre and by the specimen preparation and in a minor way by interface properties.

The rupture mechanisms

As shown previously, two types of cracks may be induced by the fibre ruptures. In a first case decohesion between the fibre and the matrix takes place and, in the second case the matrix fails. The occurrence of each mechanism will depend on the relation between the interface and the matrix properties.

In the case of the polypropylene and the epoxy resin LY556, it is clear that the interface which fails. As the interface is the weak spot and hence failure occurs at the fibre-matrix interface, the fragmentation test is appropriate for the determination of the interface properties. Nevertheless, an appropriate deduction scheme (5) has to be used to derive from the experimental results the interface decohesion strength and the interface friction stress. The Kelly's formula is not applicable in this case as the hypotheses on which the formula is based are not full-filled.

For the deduction of the interface properties the information concerning the evolution of the aspect ratio ($S=Lf/D$) and the decohesion ration ($m=2L_{dec}/Lf$) are of prime importance. Indeed, for the determination of the interface properties (decohesion shear strength and friction strength), based on a theoretical model (6), a complete fragmentation test is simulated of which the interface properties parameters are selected to obtain the best correlation with the experimental data. This procedure has to be followed as it is known that identical saturation aspect ratios may be obtained for different combinations of decohesion and friction strengths.

When a fibre fracture induces stresses in the matrix which reach critical values sooner than the interface stresses, cracks will propagate into the matrix. Two kinds of cracks may occur: the disk-shaped and the cup-cone cracks (2). The firsts are perpendicular to the fibre and can be explained by the fact that when the fibre fractures, the matrix adjacent to the filament at the fracture will be suddenly stressed (having been virtually unstressed) to carry the tension previously supported by the filament. At the exact location of the filament fracture, the stress state is primarily tension in the direction of the filament axis. The tensile strength of the matrix may be exceeded and disk-shaped crack will form at that point normal to the filament axis. The extent of this crack will be controlled by the fracture toughness of the resin.

The cup-cone cracks will arise in the matrix near the fibre ends and will make an angle of 45° with the fibre. At this region, due to the shear stresses at the fibre-matrix interface necessary for the stress build up in the fibre, high tensile stresses in the 45° direction are present. The matrix will break in this place in Mode I. Once the sudden crack initiation process has occurred, the propagation of the crack will be determined by the new state of stress in the region of the crack tips.

In the case of the Epikote 828/871 resin, at the beginning of the test, two cup-cone fractures can be seen at both sides of the fibre fracture. After the instantaneous step, the cup-cone failures evolve and the initial cracks tend to propagate in mode I perpendicular to the fibre axis. This is due to the evolution of the stress states depending on the already existing cracks.

All these results show that the failure mechanisms in the case of the Epikote resin is rather complex and encourage a careful study of the crack paths. The results show also that the matrix properties are preponderant in the application of the failure criteria. As in the formula of Kelly the matrix properties are not used to derive the interface properties and, as in this case it is not the interface which fails but the matrix, the formula may not be applied as such.

The importance of the matrix properties on the fragmentation process has already been pointed out by Monette (7) and Selvadurai (8). The latter has used the boundary element technique and quasistatic crack extension criteria, where the K_{Ic} of the matrix is taken into account, for the modelling of the matrix crack propagation during a fragmentation test. Similar approaches, where the elastic and the plastic behaviour of the matrix is taken into account, will be very helpful for the characterisation of the behaviour of the matrix region near the fibre surface.

The saturation level

We have seen that different failure mechanisms may happen during the fragmentation test. Nevertheless, a similar observation can be made for each system: a saturation level of the aspect ratio has been obtained. This level has been reached very rapidly in the case of the polypropylene and epoxy LY556 specimens where decohesion occurred and, quite slowly in the case of the Epikote resin where no decohesion was observed. An interesting fact is that the number of fibre fractures at saturation in the case of the unsized fibres is always twice the number of fractures obtained with the sized fibres whatever the resin tested. As the matrix properties do not seem to influence this fact an explanation has to be found by considering other phenomena. In a first step the constant difference between the unsized and the sized fibres could be attributed to the existing difference of tensile strength between the two fibres. Nevertheless, we may show that, even if the tensile strength plays an important role on the value of the saturation fibre length, the constant difference between the two fibres may not be explained only by the difference in tensile strength. Indeed, the results of the tensile tests carried out on fibre, with different gauge length, have shown that the difference in fibre strength between the two fibres is not the same whatever the fibre length concerned.

Another explanation for this constant difference between the two fibres can be found by considering the presence of a similar interphase region at the fibre surface whatever the resin used. The local properties of this region would be then taken into account instead of the mechanical properties of the bulk matrices.

All this shows the complexity of the interpretation of the fragmentation test results and justifies the use of appropriate tools for the exploitation of the results.

6. Conclusion

The study presented here has shown that the fragmentation process is controlled by a lot of parameters (the preparation procedure, the fibre, the interphase and the matrix properties) and that one has to take into account not only the stress states at the interface region but also the stress states in the matrix.

In the case of the two epoxy resins used, we have clearly seen two kinds of crack propagation induced by the fibre rupture. When the matrix exhibited good mechanical properties (high tensile strength and high Young's modulus) the weakest point was the interface and the energy released by the fracture of the fibre was used to propagate a rupture along the interface. On the other hand, when the matrix exhibited poor mechanical properties and a large plateau of plasticity, the fracture of the fibre enhanced the initiation of cracks in the matrix.

In the case of the polypropylene, even if this has similar mechanical tensile properties as the epoxy resin 828/87, the interface here is weak, and the crack propagation after one fibre fracture is interfacial in nature. This can be explained by the fact that the polypropylene is a non-polar molecule and consequently, adhesion between the fibre and the matrix will be the limiting factor.

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